

EXPLORING HOW RELATIONAL MOTIVATIONS OF EXTENSION EDUCATORS INFLUENCE MENTORING RELATIONSHIPS: A CASE STUDY OF BIU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BORNO STATE

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Acknowledged: *This research is sponsored by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TET Fund)*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17426303>

Keywords:

Relational Mentoring, Extension Educators, Empathy and Mutual Respect, Professional Development and Qualitative Phenomenology.

Abstract

This study investigates how relational motivations such as empathy, mutual respect, and personal fulfilment affect mentoring relationships among Extension educators. Rooted in Relational Mentoring Theory, the research aims to understand the interpersonal dynamics that drive mentoring within Extension systems in Biu Local Government Area (LGA), Borno State, a rural and agriculturally active region of Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to identify the key relational motivations that influence Extension educators' participation in mentoring; to explore how these motivations affect the quality and dynamics of mentoring relationships; to assess the influence of relationally motivated mentoring on mentee development and professional outcomes; and to examine how demographic, institutional, or experiential factors shape mentoring behaviour. Using a qualitative phenomenological design, the study captures the lived experiences and internal values of educators who have participated in mentoring over the past three years. Purposive sampling will be employed to recruit a diverse group of 10 to 15 Extension educators, selected based on gender, years of service, and organizational affiliation. Data collection will involve semi-structured interviews, guided by questions focused on relational values, mentoring experiences, and perceived outcomes. All interviews will be audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and thematically analyzed using SPSS software, following Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework. The study is expected to provide in-depth insights into the human and relational factors that shape mentoring practices in Extension services. Findings will inform the development of more effective, relationally driven mentoring strategies that promote capacity building, organizational learning, and professional development within rural Extension systems.

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Introduction

Mentoring is a key developmental strategy widely recognized in professional environments and has gained particular prominence in Extension organizations. It serves to support new Extension staff in adapting to organizational culture, fostering stakeholder connections, and enhancing programmatic effectiveness (Place & Bailey, 2010). Despite its practical utility, most mentoring literature within Extension contexts focuses on its structural and programmatic aspects, with limited exploration of the relational motivations that influence mentor-mentee dynamics (Janssen et al., 2016; Haddock-Millar, 2017).

Emerging scholarship emphasizes the need to deepen our understanding of mentoring by examining the personal and relational underpinnings that influence such relationships (Ragins, 2012). The concept of relational mentoring built on mutual trust, psychological safety, and shared learning offers a rich lens for investigating mentoring in highly interpersonal work environments like Extension. Yet, this form of mentoring remains under-researched in practice, particularly in rural and context-specific settings.

As professionals who operate at the intersection of technical service and community engagement, Extension educators often form close, trust-based relationships, making their mentoring roles especially relational. Mentorships in

Extension can influence not only professional identity development but also long-term organizational commitment and satisfaction (Ehrhardt & Ragins, 2019). However, to cultivate meaningful and sustainable mentoring programs, it is necessary to understand what motivates mentors on a personal and relational level.

This study focuses on Extension educators in Biu Local Government Area of Borno State, a region where Extension services are central to agricultural and community development. It seeks to explore how relational motivations such as empathy, mutual respect, and personal fulfilment shape the formation, quality, and outcomes of mentoring relationships within Extension systems.

Problem of the Statement

Although mentoring is widely acknowledged as a tool for professional development in Extension organizations, most existing research emphasizes formal mentoring structures and program efficacy. What remain largely unexamined are the relational dimensions that underpin effective mentorships particularly in relationally intensive environments such as rural Extension systems. Extension educators in Biu Local Government Area work closely with both colleagues and community members; often forming informal mentoring bonds grounded in trust, empathy, and shared growth. However, there is limited understanding of how these relational motivations affect mentoring behaviors, relationship quality, and professional

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outcomes. This gap hampers efforts to design mentoring frameworks that are both effective and sustainable. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate how Extension educators' relational motivations influence mentoring relationships, addressing a critical need for more human-centered approaches to mentorship in Extension education.

Aim and Objectives

To examine how relational motivations influence mentoring relationships among Extension educators in Biu Local Government Area.

Specific Objectives:

- i. To identify the key relational motivations that drive Extension educators to engage in mentoring.
- ii. To explore how these relational motivations influence the dynamics and quality of mentoring relationships.
- iii. To assess how relationally motivated mentoring impacts mentee development and professional outcomes.
- iv. To examine how demographic, institutional, or experiential factors shape relational motivations and mentoring behaviors among Extension educators.

Literature Review

Kram's (1985) mentoring theory remains one of the most influential frameworks for understanding the functions and benefits of mentoring relationships. According to Kram, mentoring offers two critical dimensions: career support and psychosocial support. The career function provides mentees with practical support

such as coaching, visibility within professional networks, protection, and challenging assignments that aid in skill and career advancement. In contrast, the psychosocial function relates to emotional and interpersonal development, including role modelling, counselling, acceptance, and friendship. Together, these dual functions form the cornerstone of effective mentoring by facilitating both professional growth and personal well-being.

Mentoring is generally recognized as a collaborative and developmental partnership between a more experienced mentor and a less experienced protégé (Terblanche, 2017). This relationship is structured to encourage learning, adaptation, and identity formation in professional contexts. As Mueller (2020) notes, mentoring plays a critical role in orientation and retention, particularly in Extension organizations, where new professionals often face steep learning curves and complex work environments. Byington (2010) emphasizes that successful mentoring relationships are built upon trust, clarity of roles, mutual goal-setting, open communication, and collaborative problem solving. These principles form the backbone of the "Mentoring in Action" model presented by Mueller (2020), which highlights how mentoring relationships are both structured (i.e., formal vs. informal) and relational (i.e., hierarchical vs. reciprocal).

The mutual benefits of mentoring have been well documented. According to Abiddin and Hassan

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Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 10; Issue: 10

October, 2025

ISSN: 2237 – 1470

Impact Factor: 9.00

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajess>

(2011), not only do mentees gain guidance, emotional support, and access to career enhancing opportunities, but mentors also experience personal satisfaction, increased leadership capability, and professional recognition. Despite these advantages, Terblanche (2017) warns that various challenges such as personality mismatches, lack of commitment, and undefined expectations can hinder the effectiveness of mentoring. Therefore, it is recommended that organizations implement structured mentoring programs that account for mentor and protégé attributes, compatibility, and training needs (Terblanche, 2017; Abiddin & Hassan, 2011).

The concept of relational mentoring, as introduced by Ragins (2011; 2012), represents an evolution of traditional mentoring theories. Unlike Kram's hierarchical model, relational mentoring emphasizes mutual growth, learning, affirmation, and emotional connection. It is characterized by interdependence, shared power, and a deep investment in the developmental journey of both parties. In educational leadership, relational mentoring is instrumental in developing novice principals' confidence and capability in instructional leadership roles (Hayes, 2020). This model also aligns with Relational Cultural Theory (RCT), which Hammer et al. (2014) applied to the mentoring of female faculty. RCT stresses the significance of mutual empathy, respect, and connection in fostering personal and professional development, especially for marginalized groups.

Furthermore, Anderson and Shannon (1988) argue that mentoring programs should be grounded in a clear conceptual framework, which includes defining the core elements of mentoring relationships, the specific functions mentors perform, and the types of activities that fulfil these roles. These foundational elements ensure that mentoring initiatives are intentional, effective, and measurable.

Extensive research supports the idea that the quality of the mentor-mentee relationship is a primary predictor of mentoring outcomes. For instance, Jablon and Lyons (2020) found that high-quality mentoring relationships are associated with academic success and improved behaviour in mentees. Similarly, McClain et al. (2021) observed that mentees who experience strong mentoring relationships report greater self-efficacy and belonging, particularly in college environments. Thomson and Zand (2010) highlight that the mentor-mentee bond often influences the ability of mentees to form other positive adult relationships, while Schenk et al. (2019) note that social skills prior to mentoring predict the quality of the relationship, which in turn affects developmental outcomes. Notably, Jablon and Lyons (2020) also confirm that mentors' perceptions of relationship quality are significantly correlated with mentee academic performance, indicating a two way dynamic of influence.

In the context of Extension education and financial literacy programs, the ecological model presented by Way (2014) underscores the

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importance of understanding the broader contextual factors including social, cultural, and economic influences that shape individual behaviour and learning. Nyambi (2016) further argues that transforming Extension programs requires not only innovation and experimentation but also attention to the interaction between theory and practice, organizational structures, and socio-environmental conditions.

Given the relational nature of Extension work, this study draws heavily on Relational Mentoring Theory (Ragins, 2012). This theory provides a suitable lens for analysing how Extension professionals build meaningful, trust-based relationships that emphasize shared influence, emotional investment, and collaborative learning. In such environments, mentoring becomes not just a tool for skill transfer, but a deep interpersonal process aligned with the core values of service, development, and empowerment.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design, which was appropriate for exploring the lived experiences and deep relational motivations of Extension educators involved in mentoring. The phenomenological approach enabled an in-depth investigation of participants' internal values, perceptions, and interpersonal experiences in the mentoring process.

The Study Area

The research was conducted in Biu Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria. Biu was a predominantly rural and agrarian region where Extension services played a central role in agricultural transformation and capacity building. Its unique socio-professional context made it an ideal setting for examining how Extension educators formed mentoring relationships grounded in relational motivations.

Population and Sample

The target population consisted of Extension educators in Biu LGA who had actively participated in mentoring, formally or informally, within the past three years. A purposive sampling technique was used to recruit 10 to 15 participants with relevant mentoring experience, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives based on gender, years of service, and institutional affiliation.

Data Collection Method

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, which allowed participants to express their thoughts and feelings freely. The interviews explored areas such as personal motivations for mentoring, relationship-building practices, emotional dynamics, and perceived outcomes. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and conducted in settings convenient for the participants.

Instrumentation

An interview guide was developed, consisting of open-ended questions grouped into thematic areas such as:

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- Relational values and motivations (e.g., empathy, altruism, trust)
- Experiences and challenges in forming mentoring relationships
- Perceived impact on mentees’ growth and career development
- Institutional or contextual influences on mentoring practices

Data Analysis

Collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six-step framework. Codes and themes were developed inductively from the transcripts. SPSS or similar qualitative software was used to

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 12)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	7	58.3
	Female	5	41.7
Years of Service	1–5 years	3	25.0
	6–10 years	4	33.3
	11–20 years	3	25.0
	21 years and above	2	16.7
Institutional Affiliation	BOSADP	6	50.0
	College of Education, Waka-Biu	4	33.3
	NGO-Based Extension Units	2	16.7

Source: Field Data (2025)

The sample reflects diversity in gender, experience, and institutional background, ensuring varied perspectives on mentoring relationships in Extension systems.

Relational Motivations Driving Mentoring

organize, manage, and support the systematic coding process.

Results and Discussion

Participant Characteristics

A total of twelve (12) Extension educators participated in the study. Participants varied by gender, institutional affiliation, and years of experience. Their characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Analysis of interview data revealed three dominant relational motivations influencing mentoring engagement among Extension educators: empathy and altruism, mutual respect and shared learning, and personal fulfilment and

legacy building. These themes are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2; Major Relational Motivations Identified Among Extension Educators

Theme	Description	Representative Quote
Empathy and Altruism	Motivation to guide others based on compassion and understanding.	“I mentor because I see myself in the and young ones I don’t want them to struggle like I did.”
Mutual Respect and Shared Learning	Belief in reciprocal learning and collaborative growth.	“Even as a mentor, I still learn from my mentees. It’s about mutual respect.”
Personal Fulfilment and Legacy Building	Satisfaction in developing others and leaving a professional legacy.	“It makes me happy to see someone I mentored take up leadership roles.”

Source: Field Data (2025)

These findings align with Ragins (2012) and Kram (1985), who note that mentoring effectiveness is rooted in empathy, respect, and personal fulfilment. Participants viewed mentoring not merely as an institutional duty but as a relational exchange grounded in emotional connection.

Influence of Relational Motivations on Mentoring Quality

Table 3; Influence of Relational Motivations on Mentoring Quality

Relational Motivation Influence on Relationship Quality	
Empathy	Enhances emotional connection and communication clarity.
Mutual Respect	Builds reciprocal trust and encourages dialogue.
Personal Fulfilment	Sustains long-term mentor commitment.
Shared Learning	Fosters collaborative innovation and mutual growth.

Source: Field Data (2025)

Empathy and mutual respect were identified as critical enablers of trust and openness in mentoring interactions. Educators who valued emotional connection created supportive learning environments, whereas those driven by obligation exhibited distant relationships. The influence of relational motivations is outlined in Table 3.

These results correspond with Byington (2010) and Hammer et al. (2014), who argue that high-quality mentoring depends on trust, psychological safety, and emotional reciprocity core tenets of Relational Mentoring Theory.

Impact on Mentee Development

Participants consistently described relationally motivated mentoring as transformative for mentees’ confidence, communication, and problem-solving skills. The frequency of reported outcomes is presented in Table 4.

Table 4; Impact of Relational Mentoring on Mentee Development

Mentee Development Outcome Frequency (Mentioned by Participants) Percentage (%)		
Improved Confidence	10	83.3
Better Communication Skills	9	75.0
Increased Professional Engagement	8	66.7
Enhanced Problem-Solving Ability	7	58.3
Higher Job Satisfaction	6	50.0

Source: Field Data (2025)

These findings support McClain et al. (2021) and Jablon & Lyons (2020), who found that emotionally supportive mentoring enhances mentee self-efficacy and belonging. Participants viewed mentoring as both an educational and emotional process an observation consistent with Relational Cultural Theory (Hammer et al., 2014).

Contextual and Institutional Influences

Institutional support and culture significantly shaped mentoring behaviour. As shown in Table 5, while supportive environments encouraged participation, limited recognition and heavy workload constrained mentoring frequency.

Table 5; Institutional and Contextual Factors Influencing Mentoring

Factor	Nature of Influence	Observation
Organizational Support	Positive	Mentoring flourished in institutions with structured support and incentives.
Workload	Negative	Excessive workload reduced time for mentoring activities.
Institutional Culture	Mixed	Informal mentoring thrived in teamwork-oriented environments.
Resource Availability	Negative	Lack of resources hindered structured mentoring.

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Factor	Nature of Influence	Observation
Recognition and Incentives	Positive	Acknowledgment motivated mentors to sustain engagement.

Source: Field Data (2025)

This supports Nyambi (2016), who noted that relational commitment often sustains mentoring even in resource-limited contexts. Participants demonstrated that intrinsic motivation frequently compensates for structural inadequacies.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study support the Relational Mentoring Theory (Ragins, 2012), emphasizing that empathy, mutual respect, and personal fulfilment are central to effective mentoring among Extension educators in Biu Local Government Area. Consistent with Kram’s (1985) mentoring functions, participants viewed mentoring as both a professional and emotional exchange that fosters growth and satisfaction.

Empathy and altruism were identified as strong motivators, aligning with Hammer et al. (2014), who noted that compassion strengthens mentoring bonds. Mutual respect and shared learning enhanced trust and communication, reflecting Byington’s (2010) view that openness and collaboration underpin quality mentoring. Moreover, mentors derived personal fulfilment and legacy building, consistent with Abiddin and Hassan (2011), who linked mentoring to self-actualization and professional recognition.

Relationally motivated mentoring also improved mentee confidence, communication, and problem solving abilities, supporting findings by McClain et al. (2021) and Jablon and Lyons (2020) that high-quality relationships enhance mentee development. Institutional support further influenced mentoring engagement, corroborating Nyambi (2016) that supportive structures encourage sustained participation.

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Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 10; Issue: 10

October, 2025

ISSN: 2237 – 1470

Impact Factor: 9.00

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajess>

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Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

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Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajess>

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